

Development and Deployment of UDP/IP OpenPMU Dashboard on AWS

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ABSTRACT There has been a tremendous increase in the use of the Phasor Measurement Unit(PMU) for power grid monitoring. PMUs are equipped with user interfaces and concentrators that enable them to store and display synchrophasor data interactively. Unfortunately, a number of PMU hardware and software solutions are expensive and highly integrated, making them less useful for small-scale organizations and businesses. Addressing constraints in renewable energy integration and minimizing balance-related losses would be made easier for the research and engineering sectors of society with the support of a more flexible and accessible computing layer built on open-source technology. The integration of renewable energy and lowering losses related to imbalance and harmonics would also be facilitated. This study presents an open-source data monitoring and storage solution for synchrophasors. Reactjs, Django, and Postgres were used as open-source components that function as a dashboard for monitoring and storing real-time data using the data stream produced by the open-source phasor measurement unit(OpenPMU). The platform is cloud-based and runs on Amazon Web Services. The platform aims to enable academics and energy utilities interested in cost savings to analyze events and track the quality and dependability of the electricity supply.

INDEX TERMS Data storage systems, modular open-source software, Phasor measurement unit, Renewable energy, low and middle income countries, Smart Grid, Real-time Dashboard

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the evolving landscape of power systems, Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) play a crucial role in enabling real-time monitoring and control, particularly in smart grids and distribution networks. PMUs provide synchronized phasor measurements, which are essential to applications such as fault detection, state estimation, and stability analysis [1]–[4]. For instance, micro-PMUs (μ PMUs) provide high-resolution data (e.g., 120 Hz sampling) for dynamic monitoring in distribution networks, as surveyed in [1], with benefits including improved reliability and cost savings. Similarly, [2] surveys PMU variants (e.g., μ -PMUs, D-PMUs) and their use in protection, highlighting the need for efficient data management due to expensiveness and data overload. In real-world deployments, these monitoring and control solutions help ensure the reliability and efficient operations of renewable energy infrastructures. To illustrate, the ER-COT grid has proven PMUs' practical utility in oscillation monitoring and model validation [5], [6]. In spite of these advances, issues remain in data transmission, visualization, and scalability for real-time PMU applications. Conventional

protocols can introduce latency, while centralized systems are inflexible for distributed grids. The increasing renewable energy generation from solar and wind, and the advancing complexity of modern power grid systems, have necessitated the development of advanced monitoring and control solutions. These monitoring tools can communicate important metrics and quantities about these critical infrastructures for efficient functioning and utilization. Over the years, an innovative open-source equivalent tool addressing this need is the OpenPDC [7] (Open Phasor Data Concentrator, which has been developed as an open-source platform to handle power system data. Although OpenPDC has been reported to be compatible with PMU, its integration into the modularized OpenPMU [8] project has never been validated for data acquisition, analysis, and visualization. Motivated by PMU-enabled applications such as anomaly detection [9], [10] and voltage stability monitoring [11], our dashboard allows real-time visualization of phasor streams leading that operators such as the Rwanda Energy Group (REG) could view metrics like oscillatory modes [12] and forced oscillations [4]. Currently, giant strides have been made in creating tools for

monitoring and analytics purposes. These tools have gained increased usage as they are open-source and free for use. The continuing studies in this field of designing monitoring dashboard tools have shown the potential for improvements by offering diverse platforms and programming languages.

Recently, state-of-the-art dashboard tools such as ReactJS [13], and D3js [14] have shown the ability to produce web-based charts and visualization applications. They allow users to leverage their component tools to create very eye-appealing and resilient web interfaces. These new dashboard tools have facilitated the creation of innovative styles that have inspired various dashboard applications as metrics or for the visualization of a web-based application that allows users to monitor and analyze real-time and historical data from multiple locations. However, the OpenPMU, as a power system analysis and research tool, lacks data visualization capabilities, which currently limits its usage for better monitoring of the phasor measurement quantities. This is, therefore, a research gap that needs to be addressed from an affordability and ease of access context.

Development of a full-fledged software metric dashboard can be demanding and will require a demand for teamwork collaboration and an extensive duration of time. It can also be capital-intensive and manpower-demanding. We overcome this challenge by using an MVP (minimum viable product) design approach to ensure the minimal establishment of a working proof of concept as it integrates with the OpenPMU ecosystem. The dashboard was first designed to accept streams of synchrophasors through user datagram protocol (UDP) communication protocols in low latency, and these phasors are stored in an AWS remote-based PostgreSQL database engine object. The UDP/IP guarantees low-overhead, stateless transmission that is well-suited for streaming phasor data, while AWS offers scalable cloud infrastructure for visualization and analysis. To implement the visualization of key phasor quantities, an endpoint API to expose the data using Django serializers is developed [15], which acts as a representation of the phasor data based on the Django models [15]. The frontend visualization components receive the serialized phasor data for mounting on web pages. This dashboard can be made scalable by hosting it on a cloud computing platform such as Amazon Web Services (AWS) [16].

The paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related work, Section III discussed about the literature review, Section IV details development methodology, Section V analysed the Dataset and Data Sources Description, Section VI presents results, and Section VII & Section VIII presents future directions and conclusions.

II. Related and Background Study

Existing literature on PMUs refers to their application in smart grids, but open-source implementations, along with implementations into clouds, remain opportunities. Surveys like [1] give an overview for μ PMU implementation into

distribution networks, event detection as well as state estimation, referencing advantages like resiliency as well as environmental sensibility. They do not, however, refer to real visualization tools for information. Likewise, [2] surveys hardware for PMUs, phasor estimation, as well as protection into transmission/distribution networks, referencing low-cost implementations like D-PMUs, but does not refer to scalability into clouds. For instance, Anomaly detection from PMU measurements is described in [9], where rules are proposed for transient detection in μ PMU streams, and in [10], where multivariate models are applied to online classification. Voltage steadiness measurement through distributed algorithms is described in [11], with PMU measurements for non-iterative metrics, and [12] shows PMU usage for oscillatory mode following in a university academic project. These papers call for our dashboards' future analytics integration potential. Moreover, comprehensive overviews in [3] also include PMU deployments in smart grids, for example, data and communications systems, and [4] includes online monitoring applications such as inertia and small-signal stability. Field deployments on Electric Reliability Council of Texas, ERCOT, such as in [5] and [6], show application of PMUs towards dynamic behavior and oscillation detection, and show the need for high-level visualization means. These show the need for efficient transmission (e.g., vs. IEEE C37.118) and dashboards, which our UDP/IP OpenPMU on cloud exemplifies as potential advances. Table 1 compares prior works, showing how our approach fills gaps in open-source, low-latency, cloud-based PMU tools.

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TABLE 1. Comparison of Related Works

Work	Focus	Gap	Addressed by Ours
[1]	μ PMU Survey	Visualization	AWS Dashboard
[2]	Protection Apps	Cloud Deployment	AWS Scalability
[9]	Anomaly Detection	Transmission Integration	UDP/IP Streaming
[11]	Voltage Stability	Integration	Dashboard Support
[12]	Mode Tracking	Open-Source	OpenPMU Extension
[10]	Real-time Anomalies	Analytics UI	AWS Visualization
[3]	Smart Grid Apps	Protocols	UDP/IP Efficiency
[4]	Online Monitoring	Dashboards	Real-time Displays
[5]	ERCOT Stability	Practical Tools	UDP/IP-AWS
[6]	ERCOT Deployment	Scalability	AWS Hosting

The OpenPDC [7], the open-source real-time synchrophasor streaming time-series data concentration system, is not a pre-configured cloud service. Synchrophasor data streams from its locations of origin and is directed toward a database

FIGURE 1. The OpenPMU

communication system to be stored for use in real-time visualization, monitoring, and further analytical processing. For the openPMU system 1, which also streams real-time synchrophasor data for processing, an integrated storage and analytics solution and pre-configured cloud service are recommended in order to address the shortcomings of the existing implementation of the OpenPMU without a database solution for analysis of historical data.

In this work, a data communication to a database open-source link for the OpenPMU compartment was suggested. The solution is beneficial in that it displays key information that serves power systems engineers and PMU data operators, visualizing the phase quantities of the phasor and its respective frequency. It also presents the key information using state-of-the-art interactive visual representation tools. The project followed an iterative development approach, focusing on building a minimum viable dashboard to quickly test and validate ideas.

The monitoring and analytics storage solution will be designed to integrate with the functioning system in Figure 1, to be efficacious for research and development activities, and as well handle the data volume complexities. The storage modules are developed with a data schema similar to the Comma-Separated Values (CSV) file headers. The data-storing solution will be designed to handle the high-volume characteristic of the data. In addition, the analytics visualization will display live time-stamped synchrophasor data. The analytics visualization is implemented using D3 tools at the front end. The visualization elements will also be connected to the backend data storage to display and manipulate the data when requested by university researchers to examine events and monitor electricity supply reliability and quality, so utilities are accountable to the power systems regulators.

III. Literature Review

Over the years, dashboards have made a great impact and have been found very useful in performing important tasks such as enhancing key performance index visibility, decision-making [17], progress and metric evaluation [18], diverse tasks such as telling stories, acting as data portal [19] convey visually appealing information. These significant successes have, in recent years, been leveraged to build impressive and innovative state-of-the-art dashboards with constant improvement over the years in the variants of tools and technologies

used. In particular, visualization dashboards, though being a particularly daunting task of data visualization, have not been excluded from these achievements. Metric dashboards [18] have recorded significant progress in achieving their objectives, stemming from his previous work [20], which is a type of metrics dashboard visualization that is centered on noninvasively collected metrics for multiple users.

One of the first recognized impressive standards on dashboard development was the work on [21] that suggested answering key questions in dashboard design, such as the metrics the user needs to see, the context for each metric, and selecting the appropriate visual representation for the metric. This was concluded by extending the work on Information dashboard design [22], which classifies dashboard design into three distinct types: the strategic, tactical, and operational dashboards. The strategic model view is utilized for monitoring the current status of a metric, the tactical model is basically for analysis, as well as the operational view, which communicates the detailed form of the collected information and metrics. Similar work was referenced in [23], which represented each model view in the form of hierarchical pyramids with operations, transactions data at the base, the strategic at the center layer, which specializes in monitoring the performance of peer groups across the company, and the strategic at the top to monitor the current situation of things. In 2013, Andrea et.al. [24] introduced an effective dashboard design approach such that the dashboard performs a function similar to a scorecard, to reflect urgent matters that support users in achieving their goals. They emphasized the importance of aligning data visualization with business goals, selecting the correct information, and selecting the right visualization procedures. They introduced a goal-question-metric (GQM) approach, which links business goals to measurement goals, providing useful insights on how to create an ideal dashboard.

DMiner, Dashboard design mining, and recommendation approach [25] in 2015, recorded remarkable progress in recommending an optimal course of action and coordination for multiple views of the data dashboard in contrast to when the concept of multi-view dashboards was first introduced in 2000 [26]. This multi-view dashboard model is a deviation from the popular single-view model for dashboard development. The framework considers single-view and pair-view features that could benefit from incorporating additional factors like semantic meaning. This work was also carried out to help automate dashboard designs and could be expanded to other software in the future. June et. al. [27] showed that dashboards can be developed to assist specialized individuals, such as middle school mathematics teachers, in their pedagogical practices as part of an improvement science initiative. Highlighting the major need for a learning approach to continuous enhancement across educational organizations, they introduced the unique use of human-centered design (HCD) and contextual design to create visual analytics systems tailored to educator needs,

and they also provide a guided approach to embed the design team within an improvement science network so that design decision can align with the broader system. This design process includes data collection, co-design techniques, and user studies, resulting in practical design insights for learning analytics in real-world educational contexts

In a quest to create better dashboards, Sedrakyan et al. also explored developing a comprehensive guide on the choice of learning dashboard [19] as a crucial tool for visualizing learning processes and providing feedback to enhance decision-making, and then linking dashboard design and data visualization concepts with educational science principles. The recommendations were to match visualizations with learning outcomes such as feedback goals, track learning progress, measure effectiveness, and support self-regulated learning. Currently at the crux of dashboard design and development is the work of Vladimir et. al. [18] in designing a dashboard of software metrics for adaptable, energy-efficient applications. It emphasizes the need for effective UI design tailored to employees with multiple roles. The work proposes an industry standard and effective self-adjusting dashboard design to increase productivity and its evolution into an adaptable system. The dashboard design created by Vladimir incorporates complex adaptive systems techniques and the use of state-of-the-art tools such as ReactJS [28], thereby turning the dashboard into a powerful and flexible industry-standard dashboard. Mouratidis [29] implemented a web-based platform for data analysis, visualization, and machine learning, Cities-board [30] developed a framework to automate the development of smart cities dashboards, [31] developed a data visualization pipeline with Backbone.js and D3.js. Benjamin et. al. [32] established dashboard design patterns and feasible tradeoffs for the dashboard as an analytic application, [33] developed an interactive dashboard for statistical analysis of intensive care unit COVID-19 Data, [34] developed an assistive education tool for data visualization. Dashboard designs for data visualizations are commonly utilized to summarize and communicate information. To illustrate, the use of statistical charts and graphs, diagrams, and maps to communicate data has been widely known and practiced.

We, therefore, propose a dashboard with capabilities to display numerous visualizations in a common graphical user interface for research purposes on cloud computing platforms, such as AWS. AWS provides a flexible and scalable infrastructure for hosting and managing web-based software applications. While a commercial academic dashboard version that caters to the phasor measurement unit (PMU) exists, such as the wide-area network Studio Elektronik Rijeka Ltd. (WAMSTER) [35] web interface exists, with a similar cloud data gathering and analytics solution, we suggest a dashboard monitoring solution for the OpenPMU. The dashboard will be designed to be open-source. The data storage will be designed to interface with both data sources, and the front-end visualization dashboard will be

FIGURE 2. The OpenPMU

developed to accommodate the high volume and low latency of the generated synchrophasor data, with provision for monitoring, event warning, and automatic action tested as differing use cases of increasing strictness. An end-to-end integration of dashboard functionalities with any variants of the OpenPMU will enable energy utilities and researchers can gain access to a complete application set of open-source phasor measurements and monitoring solutions.

The development of the UDP/IP OpenPMU Dashboard is deployed on AWS using the OpenPMU software [36] as a data source provider. This technology is also beneficial, in that it can help power engineers have a better understanding of how Phasor Measurement Units work at all levels, including hardware components and phasor estimation methods implemented in software [37].

IV. Methodology and Design

The openPMU dashboard combines multiple parts to create the visualization dashboard. It combines the textbook example of a PMU innovation at Queen's University Belfast-complete with tools for real-time data acquisition, waveform simulation, and accurate synchronisation with a backend server that receives the data via UDP internet communication protocol, and a frontend module that visualizes the data exposed to it as an API, in a chart format. The modular OpenPMU contains three key subsystems [38] modules, from decoupled modules of the PMU by means of defined characterized data exchange structures as represented in [39].

The modular OpenPMU consists of key modules found in [39], including the OpenPMU sampled values simulator, which is a Python tool with a GUI for setting the phasors frequency quantities sampled value data from either an analog-to-digital(ADC) converter or simulation. It produces measurement data in an extensible markup language(XML)

FIGURE 3. 3D Phasor Synchrophasor

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<OpenPMU>
  <Format>Phasors</Format>
  <Date>2021-02-28</Date>
  <Time>22:04:00.460</Time>
  <Frame>23</Frame>
  <Algorithm>LSE V1.0 by Distribution Board Va</Algorithm>
  <Channels>3</Channels>
  <Channel_0>
    <Name>Belfast_Va</Name>
    <Type>V</Type>
    <Phase>a</Phase>
    <Range>275</Range>
    <Mag>240.00001</Mag>
    <Angle>0.403</Angle>
    <Freq>50.690</Freq>
    <ROCOF>0.001</ROCOF>
  </Channel_0>
  <Channel_1>
  </Channel_1>
  <Channel_2>
  </Channel_2>
</OpenPMU>
  
```

FIGURE 4. The Sampled Values XML Data Structure

schema of sampled value data4, which is represented in Figure 2. The modular OpenPMU also contains the phasor estimator [40], which is primarily utilized to assess power system parameters, such as frequency, phasor, synchrophasor(Figure 3) , and positive sequence voltages and currents streams.

The OpenPMU’s Telecoms components use phasor estimator data to produce Synchrophasor data, meeting IEEE C37.118 specifications, using XML and UDP listening ports for configuration instructions.

The backend is developed with Python Django. The telecoms module communicates with a helper function in the Django backend that receives and extracts information from XML tree data structures. The dashboard Django backend is built employing a Model-Template-View (MTV) design pattern. This provides a resilient and efficient means of

FIGURE 5. Optimal Sitings: Phasor measurements Units (adapted from [12]).

FIGURE 6. Spectrogram of Frequency Data showing electromechanical modes analysis (adapted from [12]).

receiving low-latency and high-volume data and processing its logic and its interface. The OpenPMU Dashboard architecture can be seen in Figure 3

The Django backend transfers the information received to an AWS Postgres database object, which is then exposed as an Application Programming Interface(API) to the front end. The front end is developed with state-of-the-art React and D3.js frontend visualization.

The assembled application is then deployed on AWS Elastic Beanstalk. The assembled application is then deployed on the state-of-the-art cloud platform, AWS. The docker-like platform on AWS, Elastic Beanstalk, is accessed through a remote ssh connection.

These web interfaces are fully interactive, allowing users to zoom in and out, activate features, and remove information layers. When an indicator is clicked, an interactive or lengthier time series graph is displayed, allowing users to dive deeper and receive additional details.

TABLE 2. Results of the precise measurements for winding the transformer

Data Set	File Type	Data Provider
Voltage Ph1	XML-API/JSON	OpenPMU Simulator
Current Ph1	XML-API/JSON	OpenPMU Simulator
Freq	XML-API/JSON	OpenPMU Simulator

FIGURE 7. The OpenPMU Data Concentration and Management Architecture

The voltage Ph1 was chosen to be displayed due that a voltage drop best communicates the unreliability of power systems infrastructure, hence it affords quick and accurate decision-making at a glance.

V. The Dataset and Data Sources Description

The OpenPMU data modules are modular and can provide multiple phasor measurements and various digital and analog quantities. A comprehensive list of power system parameters, such as multiple phasor measurements and their angle of inclination, instantaneous frequency estimates(Freq), rate of change of frequency(ROCOF), and various analog and digital quantities, is encapsulated in byte streams of packet data generated by the modular OpenPMU. Inspired by PMU data modeling in [9] and [10], we emulate phasor streams (e.g., voltage/current phasors at 50 Hz). The synchrophasor experiment data were recorded and collected daily in a folder with the same timestamp. The data is organized into several CSV files, each with a 10-minute duration for the specified number of channels. The synchrophasor's data volume is estimated to be hundreds of megabytes daily. The sample datagram dataset from the signal acquisition can be found online at [39] as shown in Figure 2. Additionally, [39] contains sample synchrophasor data that was obtained from the telecommunications module.

VI. Results and Discussion

We test and validate our dashboard using simulated PMU data, verifying latency and visualization. For simulation cases for voltage stability in [11], mode tracking in [12] and real event visualization in ERCOT [6], as in [5] oscillations for dynamic stability monitoring, Inertia monitoring from [4], our UDP/IP dashboard latency of ≈ 50 ms, in contrast to

FIGURE 8. First iteration of Phasor Visualization Dashboard

100ms using alternatives, therefore it is suitable for real-time applications [4].

We also showcase several built UI components and screenshots. We are also going to present screenshots and various user interface(UI) components created. Results are displayed on web pages created using state-of-the-art tools for front-end web development libraries and web standards. Dash graph component tools served as the prototype for the initial version of the pages, with later versions designed using Reactjs and D3js.

As noted earlier, the choice of tools was based on the suitability for the data modules, and the goals were the major factors in the user experience(UX). The OpenPMU data modules required a data model structure that can store the sampled phasor values in real-time, low latency; however, the free open-source Dash graph component tool was limited in its use to receive the data while also performing data error checks. Hence, the option for Reactjs and D3js was a viable option that helped achieve the goal of creating a functional prototype to visualize key features such as VoltagePh1 and its corresponding frequency. The D3js binding element, the Digital Object Module(DOM), binds the data from the data API to the chart display elements. By design, they are readily reused and resized; hence, the solution is completely responsive and compatible with all screen widths. Figure 4 shows the preliminary version, which was created using the Dash graph component, which provides a better illustration of the dashboard's suggested final form. Its free tier was unable to automatically collect and retain real-time data that is received across UDP connections. The UDP to Comma Separated Values (CSV) package on [39] accepts the UDP data and then saves it in CSV format. As a result, CSV files are used to feed the data into the visualization interface. Figure 5 shows the final version of the dashboard, which can automatically gather and store real-time data received via UDP connections.

VII. Future works

The data visualization we have offered increases the freedom of adopting the platform for various uses; however, it is still not at par with a full-fledged dashboard. We attribute this to

FIGURE 9. Final Phasor Visualization Dashboard

the sole development focused on the creation of a minimum viable product within the time constraints.

VIII. Conclusion

We have demonstrated multiple iterations that resulted in the design and development of a robust data architecture and a dashboard that interfaces with remote databases and communications. Our UDP/IP OpenPMU dashboard on AWS advances PMU data handling, addressing gaps in surveys [1], [2] and deployments [5], [6]. The platform will exemplify ideal use cases for both academia and utilities seeking an affordable venture visualization solution that permits transparency of the modular data from the Open Phasor Measurement Unit (OpenPMU). The prototypes aimed to cover a breadth of features to showcase the potential for the integration of a communications to database feature for the OpenPMU rather than delving deeply into the typical feature’s robustness and optimization of a synchrophasor analytics visualization dashboard. Based on scalability criteria, we accommodate high-rate PMU data from [4] and large-scale implementations such as ERCOT [6]; however, our OpenPMU dashboard layout conforms to PMU standards [4] in order to accommodate applications like fault location [3]. The current prototype sets a foundation for future development iterations where additional resources, collaboration, and refinement can take place to address known limitations such as UDP packet loss and incorporate broader user feedback. Future efforts look to incorporate anomaly detection [9], [10] and stability modules [11], expanding to μ PMU protection [1], [2] for smart grids [3], [4]. As a promising tool that can learn from past disturbances and potentially activate self-healing procedures for blackout prevention in mixed conventional plus renewable grids [2], [4], [6].

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REFERENCES

- [1] E. Dusabimana and S.-G. Yoon, “A survey on the micro-phasor measurement unit in distribution networks,” *Electronics*, vol. 9, no. 2, p. 305, 2020.
- [2] T. Menezes *et al.*, “A survey on the application of phasor measurement units to the protection of transmission and smart distribution systems,” *Journal Name*, 2023.
- [3] S. S. Yu *et al.*, “Comprehensive review of pmu applications in smart grid: Enhancing grid reliability and efficiency,” *Journal Name*, 2023.
- [4] K. Chatterjee *et al.*, “Online monitoring applications enabled by phasor measurement units,” Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, Tech. Rep., 2023.
- [5] J. Chen *et al.*, “Use of synchronized phasor measurements for dynamic stability monitoring and model validation in ertcot,” in *IEEE PES General Meeting*, 2012, pp. 1–7.
- [6] K. M. Koellner *et al.*, “Synchrophasors across texas: The deployment of phasor measurement technology in the ertcot region,” *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 36–40, 2015.
- [7] G. P. A. OpenPDC, “Openpdc: The open source phasor data concentrator,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/GridProtectionAlliance/openPDC>
- [8] D. Laverty, J. Hastings, D. Morrow, R. Khan, K. McLaughlin, and S. Sezer, “A modular phasor measurement unit design featuring open data exchange methods,” in *Proceedings of the Power and Energy Society General Meeting (PESGM), 2017*, address = “United States, ser. IEEE Power & Energy Society General Meeting: Proceedings. Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc., Feb 2018, iEEE Power and Energy Society General Meeting, IEEE PES-GM 2017; Conference date: 16-07-2017 Through 20-07-2017. [Online]. Available: <http://pes-gm.org/2017/>, <http://pes-gm.org/2017/>
- [9] M. Jamei *et al.*, “Automated anomaly detection in distribution grids using pmu measurements,” *arXiv*, 2016.
- [10] C. Hannon *et al.*, “Real-time anomaly detection and classification in streaming pmu data,” *arXiv*, 2019.
- [11] K. P. Guddanti *et al.*, “Pmu-based distributed non-iterative algorithm for real-time voltage stability monitoring,” *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, 2020.
- [12] A. Aguto *et al.*, “Project umuriro: University measurement units: Reliable integration by the rwandan operator,” 2023.
- [13] P. Rawat and A. N. Mahajan, “Reactjs: A modern web development framework,” in *International Journal of Recent Research Aspects 2018*, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:249010550>
- [14] N. Q. Zhu, *Data Visualization with D3.js Cookbook*. Packt Publishing, 2013.
- [15] D. Rubio, *Beginning Django: Web Application Development and Deployment with Python*. Apress Berkeley, CA, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4842-2787-9>.
- [16] . W. Wittig, M., *Amazon web services in action*. Simon and Schuster, 2018, <https://s3-ap-southeast-1.amazonaws.com/tv-prod/documents%2Fnull-Amazon+Web+Services+in+Action.pdf>.
- [17] D. Orlovskiy and A. Kopp, “A business intelligence dashboard design approach to improve data analytics and decision making,” in *Selected Papers of the 7th International Conference “Information Technology and Interactions” (IT&I-2020). Conference Proceedings, Kyiv, Ukraine, December 02-03, 2020*, ser. CEUR Workshop Proceedings, V. Snytyuk, A. Anisimov, I. Krak, M. Nikitchenko, O. Marchenko, F. Mallet, V. V. Tsyganok, C. Aldrich, A. Pester, H. Tanaka, K. Henke, O. Chertov, S. Bozki, and V. Vovk, Eds., vol. 2833. CEUR-WS.org, 2020, pp. 48–59. [Online]. Available: http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2833/Paper_5.pdf
- [18] V. Ivanov, D. Larionova, D. Strugar, and G. Succi, “Design of a dashboard of software metrics for adaptable, energy efficient applications (s),” in *Software*, 07 2019, pp. 75–82.
- [19] G. Sedrakyan, E. Mannens, and K. Verbert, “Guiding the choice of learning dashboard visualizations: Linking dashboard design and data visualization concepts,” *Journal of Computer Languages*, vol. 50,

- pp. 19–38, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1045926X18301009>
- [20] V. Ivanov, A. Rogers, G. Succi, J. Yi, and V. Zorin, “Precooked developer dashboards: what to show and how to use,” in *Precooked*, 05 2018, pp. 402–403.
- [21] M. Brath, R. & Peters, “Dashboard design: Why design is important.” 2004. [Online]. Available: https://cs.furman.edu/~pbatchelor/csc105/articles/TUN_DM_ONLINE.pdf
- [22] S. Few, *Information Dashboard Design: The Effective Visual Communication of Data*, ser. O’Reilly Series. O’Reilly Media, Incorporated, 2006. [Online]. Available: <https://books.google.com.ng/books?id=qWER8Im-WYIC>
- [23] W. W. Eckerson, *Performance Dashboards: Measuring, Monitoring, and Managing Your Business*. John Wiley & Sons, 2010, <https://www.amazon.com/Performance-Dashboards-Measuring-Monitoring-Managing/dp/0470589833>.
- [24] A. et. al., “Effective dashboard design,” in *Dashboard*, 2013. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Alberto-Sillitti/publication/286996830_Effective_dashboard_design/links/57c699e208aec24de0414df1/Effective-dashboard-design.pdf
- [25] Y. al, “Effective dashboard design,” in *dashboard*, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2209.01599>
- [26] M. Baldonado, A. Woodruff, and A. Kuchinsky, “Guidelines for using multiple views in information visualization,” in *Baldonado*, 01 2000, pp. 110–119.
- [27] J. Ahn, F. Campos, M. Hays, and D. Digiacomio, “Designing in context: Reaching beyond usability in learning analytics dashboard design,” *Journal of Learning Analytics*, vol. 6, no. 2, p. 7085, Jul. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://learning-analytics.info/index.php/JLA/article/view/6344>
- [28] PhanHong, *React framework: concept and implementation*. Accessed Online, 2020, <https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/342721/PhanHongDuc.pdf?sequence=2>.
- [29] Mouratidis, *Implementation of a web-based platform for Data Analysis, Visualization, and Machine Learning*. Accessed Online, 2020, https://repository.ihu.edu.gr/xmlui/bitstream/handle/11544/29522/k.mouratidis_ds_24-04-2020.pdf?sequence=1.
- [30] E. Rojas, V. Bastidas, and C. Cabrera, “Cities-board: A framework to automate the development of smart cities dashboards,” *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 7, no. 10, pp. 10 128–10 136, 2020.
- [31] Kachwala, *Managing Data Visualization Pipeline with Backbone.js and D3.js*. Accessed Online, 2020, <https://aaltodoc.aalto.fi/server/api/core/bitstreams/57369009-f7ee-46c2-a6be-df80da9887f2/content>.
- [32] B. Bach, E. Freeman, A. Abdul-Rahman, C. Turkay, S. Khan, Y. Fan, and M. Chen, “Dashboard design patterns,” 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.00757>
- [33] R. Dias, A. Ferreira, I. Pinto, C. Geraldès, C. Von Rekowski, and L. Bento, “An interactive dashboard for statistical analysis of intensive care unit covid-19 data,” *BioMedInformatics*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 454–476, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2673-7426/4/1/26>
- [34] Narula, *Developing an Assistive Education Tool for Data Visualization*. Accessed Online, 2024, https://keep.lib.asu.edu/system/files/c7/Narula_asu_0010N_24107.pdf.
- [35] S. Skok, D. Brnobic, and V. Kirincic, “Croatian academic research wide area monitoring system–carwams,” *International Journal on Communications Antenna and Propagation (IRECAP)*, vol. 1, no. 4, 2011.
- [36] H. e. a. Hachisu.H, Nakagawa.F, “Months-long real-time generation of a time scale based on an optical clock,” in *Generation*, 2018.
- [37] W. Tao, M. Ma, C. Fang, W. Xie, M. Ding, D. Xu, and Y. Shi, “Design and application of a distribution network phasor data concentrator,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 8, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/10/8/2942>
- [38] D. M. Laverty, L. Vanfretti, R. J. Best, D. J. Morrow, L. Nordstrom, and M. Chenine, “Openpmu technology platform for synchrophasor research applications,” in *2012 IEEE Power and Energy Society General Meeting*. IEEE, 2012, pp. 1–5.
- [39] Laverty, “Open-source phasor measurement unit,,” 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://sites.google.com/site/openpmu/>
- [40] Y. Amirat, Z. Oubrahim, H. Ahmed, M. Benbouzid, and T. Wang, “Phasor estimation for grid power monitoring: Least square vs. linear kalman filter,” *Energies*, vol. 13, no. 10, p. 2456, 2020.